

Legal Interpreters' View on the Feedback from Users: A Case Study in Bali

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ABSTRACT: The high volume of legal cases involving foreigners in Indonesia underscores the necessity for proficient legal interpreters, as not all foreigners possess a fluent command of the Indonesian language. As a result, the presence of legal interpreters is essential to aid foreigners navigating the legal system. The initial phase of research, which assessed the effectiveness and user experiences of legal interpreters in assisting foreigners throughout the legal proceedings, revealed that police officers engaged two categories of interpreters: ad hoc and professional interpreters. Ad hoc interpreters are temporary interpreters enlisted for specific purposes such as reporting or particular activities. These interpreters may include individuals like tour guides, drivers, spouses of foreigners, family members, and even household staff. On occasion, police officers also utilized colleagues, fellow officers, prosecutors, or lawyers proficient in English to act as legal interpreters. In contrast, professional interpreters often possess certification from reputable institutions, such as universities, translators' associations, or English language colleges, ensuring a strong command of English. According to perspectives from police officers, prosecutors, and lawyers, ad hoc interpreters tend to lack linguistic expertise and interpreting skills, leading to subpar interpretation quality. Conversely, professional interpreters exhibit superior linguistic knowledge and are largely proficient in interpreting, resulting in significantly improved interpretation services compared to ad hoc options. Legal practitioners who employ professional interpreters find their assistance invaluable. However, from the viewpoint of detainees, in-house interpreters or interpreters associated with law offices have a tendency to cast suspicion on the foreigners they assist and may steer them toward confessing to what the lawyers desire.

Based on the results and discussion, it has been determined that non-professional interpreters correspond to the ad hoc interpreters as described in the initial year of research. The interpreters of this category engage in interpretation tasks only occasionally, typically ranging from 1 to 4 instances over a span of 1 to 2 years. Professional interpreters, on the contrary, are skilled language mediators proficient in English, possessing expertise in various interpreting methods, especially in legal contexts. They are affiliated with professional associations and boast over three years of practical experience. Out of a group of 10 proficient interpreters who responded to the questionnaires, three are employed full-time, while the remaining seven operate as independent freelancers. Among the three full-time interpreters, one is stationed in-house. However, these interpreters did not completely concur with the feedback provided by users. Out of the fifteen feedback points submitted by users, a majority believed that the feedback was somewhat inaccurate. Nonetheless, some points were acknowledged for valid reasons: Firstly, considering the high volume of cases presented at the police office, the interpreters might not be well-versed in all the requisite legal terminology. Additionally, not all legal interpreters have been involved in police office proceedings, which results in an unfamiliarity with interrogation methods and procedures. Secondly, instances of interpreters displaying partiality and assisting foreign clients could stem from a lack of comprehension regarding the ethical guidelines governing legal interpreters. Misunderstandings might arise from payment arrangements, briefings, and directives received from supervisors (in the case of in-house interpreters) or from the police (for freelancers). The involvement of lawyers, foreigners, or the police in their compensation might lead to interpreters providing advice, suggestions, and direction for foreigners to admit certain actions. However, only a small subset of interpreters is inclined to do so, while the majority refrains from such actions.

KEYWORDS: legal interpreting, interpreter, users of legal interpreters

I. INTRODUCTION

Global recognition of Bali as a sought-after tourist destination is widely acknowledged. In fact, Bali often holds greater familiarity among tourists than the entire country of Indonesia due to its captivating landscapes, the warm hospitality of its inhabitants, and its distinct cultural heritage. This influx of tourists contributes positively to the local economy and raises the overall living standards of Balinese residents, particularly those engaged in the tourism industry. However, not all aspects of tourism in Bali yield favorable outcomes. The adverse consequences brought about by tourists also impact the local population. The Balinese people are intimately

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connected with these negative effects, which encompass shifts in clothing trends, the diminishing importance of the Balinese language as a cultural support, and alterations in traditional ways of life.

Aside from impacting regional languages and contributing to cultural decline, it is imperative to carefully consider the implications of drug abuse, cybercrimes involving transactions, human trafficking, and even instances of homicide. These offenses are committed by both foreign nationals and Indonesian citizens, particularly in cases related to electronic transactions and drug-related activities. Numerous instances of criminal activities involving foreigners have occurred in Bali over the past decade. Among these, drug addiction remains the most prevalent, followed by instances of fraud and misappropriation. Additionally, there has been a recent surge in skimming activities (Ana, 2018).

Data extracted from the case register of the District Court of Denpasar reveals that a total of 87 civil cases of diverse nature were recorded within the last three years. Examples of these cases include divorce proceedings, tort claims, petitions, and determinations (Ana, 2021; Ana, Susini, and Subagia, 2022). In the context of criminal cases involving foreigners, interpreters play a pivotal role in facilitating legal processes, spanning from the initial police inspection and investigation phase to the transfer to the prosecutor's office and subsequent court trial proceedings. Interpreters streamline communication between law enforcement officials and individuals who are suspected, accused, or under investigation (Cao, 2007; Nakane, 2009; Cao and Zhao, 2013).

Notably, interpreters and translators hold a significant role in facilitating advanced communication, as highlighted by Cranefield and Yoong (2007) and PöCHHACKER (2009). Moreover, their importance is growing as facilitators in various business interactions, both between corporations and individuals (Effendi, 2008).

The presence of an interpreter in this case aims at ensuring the success of communication (Nakane, 2009; Oxburgh *et al.*, 2015), for example, all things and messages in a particular dialog are understood by all relevant parties (Puspani, 2010). Without an interpreter present, a legal proceeding involving foreigners is prohibited due to the important role he performs and the fact that his participation is required by law; as a result, the proceeding is seen as being null and void. Due to their prominence and status, legal interpreters should be competent in their working language pairs. They should have knowledge of the legal system and interpreting skill (González, Vásquez and Mikkelsen, 1991; Mikkelsen, 1998).

Legal interpreters hold a crucial role within court proceedings (Monteoliva-Garcia, 2018; Hale, 2020). Accurate legal interpretation involves translating messages precisely from the source language to the target language (González, Vásquez, and Mikkelsen, 1991; Russell, 2000; Hale, 2020; De Jongh, 2008). Any deviation could result in the improper application of provisions, potentially leading to incorrect judgments. In the most severe instances, the interpretation itself could determine the fate of a defendant. Consequently, professional interpreters are indispensable in legal contexts. Recognizing their significant role, it is unjust to solely assess interpreter performance from the user's perspective. It is equally important to allow interpreters the opportunity to respond to user feedback and to investigate the challenges that contribute to such feedback.

Beyond bridging language barriers, interpreters sometimes find themselves functioning as aids to clients or legal representatives. Some individuals accept this role without a clear understanding of the interpreter's duties and responsibilities. As the results, some feedbacks were given to the interpreters from their performance. This study endeavors to address these issues comprehensively, ensuring that everyone involved comprehends the interpreter's role and knows how to effectively collaborate with trained interpreters.

Given the aforementioned backdrop, research on legal interpreters is essential because there are few studies or publications on the topic. According to the findings of the first term research project, which looked at how legal interpreters assisted foreigners in the legal system through interviews with police officers, prosecutions, and court examinations, it was discovered that police officers used both ad hoc and professional interpreters. Ad hoc interpreters are those who serve on a temporary basis, such as for reporting purposes only or specific activities. These translators may be tour guides, drivers, the spouses or partners of the foreign visitors, members of their families, or even housekeepers. On rare occasions, the police officers also used other police officers, prosecutors, or English-speaking lawyers and attorneys as legal interpreters. While qualified interpreters with a strong command of English may be licensed interpreters or interpreters from universities, the translators' association, or English colleges. Ad hoc interpreters, in the eyes of police officers, prosecutors, and attorneys, have less command of linguistics expertise and even no interpreting abilities, so the quality of the translating provided is less than satisfactory. Professional interpreters, on the other hand, typically possess interpreting skills and have greater linguistics understanding. Thus, interpreting services provided much better than ad hoc ones. And the legal officers who used them felt that they were highly beneficial. Yet, from the perspective of the detainees, the translators from the law office tended to accuse the foreigners getting aid of guilt and compelled them to say what the lawyers wanted.

In addition to the aforementioned background, research on legal interpreting received less attention (Bancroft *et al.*, 2013) from researchers, particularly in Indonesia. This can be seen from the results of publication on legal interpreting available or found both in online media (*online*) and printed media (Monteoliva-Garcia, 2018). There are, however, some researches related to legal interpreting found which can be used as comparisons in research. Those researches related to legal interpreting are described below. Alan (2001) in his article entitled "*Is the Simultaneous Mode Feasible and Desirable in Court?*": *The Hong Kong Experience and Experiment* attempted to compare consecutive and simultaneous community interpreting applied at court, taking place in Hong Kong courts. Under Hong Kong court regulations, consecutive interpreting is used at the time of examination and trial. Meanwhile,

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the simultaneous mode is only used when the judge reads out the court verdict. The interpreter sat next to the accused and interpreted the court verdict to the accused. Based on the court report where the simultaneous interpreting took place, there were four major problems that made simultaneous interpreting difficult. The four problems are (1) many inaccuracies were found in simultaneous interpreting, such as omission of information, less accurate interpretation, and use of inappropriate diction; (2) the speed of interpreting amongst interpreters were different, so that one interpreter and another interpreter could produce different terms; (3) simultaneous interpreting should follow the rhythm and speed of the speaker, as the interpreter cannot control and follow the speed of the speaker; (4) During the trial, there was a change of speaker causing the interpreter had difficulty managing it.

Jacobson, (2001) in his article entitled *Addition in Court Interpreting* focused his study on the addition of information in court interpreting in Denmark. *National Commissioner of the Danish Police* stated that interpreters should be subject to the four principles as stated in *Instructions for Interpreters*, namely (1) *accuracy and completeness*, (2) *impartiality*, (3) *confidentiality*, and (4) *conflict of interest*. In this case, a legal interpreter functions as if a machine translator. The interpreter only interprets and should translate everything accurately. However, due to the differences of language and legal systems and cultures between the source language and the target language, additional information is required to produce an accurate, acceptable and understandable interpreting for clients. What was stated by Jacobson (2001) is in line and very closely related to the result of research conducted by Puspani (2010). Puspani identified and elaborate the phenomenon of adding information in court interpreting taking place at the District Court of Denpasar. And furthermore, Puspani focuses on the impact of adding information, reducing information and shifting strategies applied by interpreters on the quality of interpreting at the District Court of Denpasar.

Ana (2018) in his article entitled "The Challenge of Interpreters in Translating in Court" stated that there are several challenges for interpreters assisting foreign accused in court. These challenges were (1) the media (both printed media and radio and television media) greatly disturbed the interpreter's concentration, due to interpreter's concerns that he would make mistakes in carrying out his duties as an interpreter; (2) the voice of accused was weak so that the interpreter had difficulty to understand the message conveyed by the accused; (3) related sounds (linked) especially foreign accused having American accent. To overcome this challenge, an interpreter applied strategies of adding and omitting messages, as well as strategy of shift as proposed by Puspani (2010). In addition, Ana (2018) proposes non-technical strategies in the efforts to overcome these difficulties, namely: by observing facial expressions, body movements (gestures) and shape of mouth and lips.

All the researches above focused on the linguistics points of the interpreters, and none of them strived to find out the reasons why such circumstance existed. This research provides the answer why the interpreters made mistakes and broken the ethic code of interpreters.

To analyzed the problems of this research some theories were applied. Jacobson (2001 in Puspani, 2010: xiii) states that interpreters should be subject to four principles, as stated in the *Instructions for Interpreters*, that are: (1) *accuracy and completeness*, (2) *impartiality*, (3) *confidentiality*, and (4) *conflict of interest*. Therefore, an interpreter only interprets and should translate everything accurately. However, it should also be borne in mind that in addition to the differences in language and legal systems, the culture between the source language and the target language is also different, so interpreters sometimes need to add or omit information in order to produce an accurate, acceptable and easily understood by the accused, and law enforcement, without affecting the content of the message conveyed.

Court interpreting is a phenomenon involving two different languages with the aim of getting the equivalent meaning of the source language and the target language. Therefore, one theory is not sufficient to cover the existing phenomena, so the eclectic theory is applied. As a basic theory is the theory of interpreting combined with the theory of syntax, semantics, pragmatics and semiotics. Berk-Seligson (1999) stated that interpreters were often encountered with problems related to court interpreting focusing on interpreters and court personnel: prosecutors, judges, accused, lawyers and witnesses. Pochhaker (2004) said that:

"an activity consisting mainly in the production of utterances (text) which are presumed to have similar meaning and/or effect as the previous existing utterances in another language and culture."

From this quotation, an interpreter is required to produce utterances that are considered to have meanings and effects that are equivalent/similar to previous utterances in different languages and cultures. The role of syntactic, semantic, pragmatic, and semiotic theories is very important for the interpreter, because in producing the results of his oral translation, he needs to consider the form of the sentence first, then look at its meaning to get equivalence, and so that the resulting equivalence is in accordance with the pragmatic theory playing a prominent role. It is not, however, as easy as imagined, an accused is often unclear in uttering words, phrases, sentences and even without speech at all, only in the form of gestures. To understand and interpreting things like this, semiotic theory plays an important role.

In the realm of law, community-based oral interpreters play a vital role in aiding individuals from foreign backgrounds who require assistance or are entangled in legal issues within Indonesia. This aligns with the provisions set forth in Law no. 24 of 2009, which pertains to the national emblem, flag, language, and national anthem. The section pertaining to the utilization of the Indonesian language, as delineated from Article 26 to Article 40 of Law no. 24 of 2009, mandates the use of the Indonesian language in all official endeavors, encompassing both spoken and written communication. In accordance with this legal framework, it becomes

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imperative to provide foreigners with the services of an interpreter to facilitate the translation of Indonesian content into the pertinent foreign language. Therefore, the primary objective of this research is to:

1. Find out the reasons of the users' feedback to the legal interpreters?
2. Find out the problems encountered by the police interpreters?
3. Seek for solution to resolve the issues and difficulties?

II. METHOD

A. Types and Sources of Data

This study constitutes field research utilizing a descriptive qualitative research approach. The research data comprises qualitative information obtained through questionnaires and structured interviews involving 12 legal interpreters. The interviewed interpreters were chosen based on their prior experience collaborating with legal authorities such as police officers, prosecutors, lawyers, and judges across various courtroom cases. The initial phase involves the interpreters responding to questionnaires distributed via the WhatsApp application. Subsequently, they undergo structured interviews, adhering to a predetermined set of questions meticulously formulated by the researchers. Prior to the interview, communication is established with the interpreters as respondents to facilitate scheduling and preparation for the forthcoming interview.

B. Research Instruments

The instruments employed in this research are categorized into two main groups. The first category consists of items associated with the interview procedure, encompassing a list of questions provided to the legal interpreters. The second category encompasses essential equipment such as recorders, video and audio cameras, stationery, paper, notebooks, computers, and printers. This assortment of equipment is utilized to capture, compile, and document the data gathered from respondents, as well as to analyze the acquired information. To accommodate potential scheduling constraints faced by participants due to their commitments, online interviews will be arranged, granting them greater flexibility in selecting suitable time slots.

C. Data Collection Methods and Techniques

The data collection process for this study comprises two distinct stages. Initially, questionnaires are administered to interpreters through the WhatsApp application to elicit preliminary feedback concerning user-submitted feedback. Subsequently, in order to validate the questionnaire outcomes, in-person interviews are undertaken. These interviews are scheduled after securing prior appointments with the respondents. Given the interpreters' demanding schedules, the interview timing and location are meticulously tailored to their availability. For those who are unable to participate in face-to-face interviews, virtual interviews will be arranged as a viable alternative. Following the interviews, the obtained results will be transcribed to facilitate subsequent analysis.

In cases where data appears ambiguous or necessitates validation, supplementary information may be sought. If required, additional interviews will be arranged, either through direct telephone conversations or via the WhatsApp application. This ensures a comprehensive and accurate examination of the data.

D. Methods and Techniques of Data Analysis

The data that have been collected will be calculated. Then the amount of the data will be classified according to the theme (thematic analysis). This is to identify patterns and to find themes of what people tell through the interviews.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is commonly assumed that law enforcement personnel, including police officers, prosecutors, and lawyers, possess proficient English skills, encompassing both written and spoken aspects. While this assumption might hold true for general English usage, it doesn't necessarily apply to specialized forms of English, such as legal English often employed within legal contexts (Alcaraz and Hughes, 2002). Consequently, when dealing with cases involving individuals from foreign countries, the assistance of interpreters becomes necessary to bridge the communication gap between law enforcement and these foreign parties. The law enforcers' experiences and perceptions of working with various interpreters tend to vary. This variance is inevitable due to the diversity of cases handled, the cultural backgrounds of the foreigners, the interpreters' differing experiences, language proficiency, and other factors.

For the purpose of this study, the interpreters are categorized into two, namely non-professional interpreters and professional ones. The results of research conducted in collaboration with RMIT University reveal the following findings:

A. Non-Professional Interpreters

Six questionnaires were delivered to non-professional legal interpreters (we commonly call newbie legal interpreters) through WhatsApp application, whose number obtained from police officers. Out of six questionnaires delivered, four interpreters answered the questionnaires and sent them back to the Warmadewa University research team. The answers are tabulated and the results are recapitulated below:

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Table. 1 Non-Professional Legal Interpreters' Responses to Users' Feedback

No.	Questions	Response
1.	How long have you been practicing as legal interpreter?	-1 – 2 years -only 2-4 times
2.	Are you a full-time interpreter?	No.
3.	If 'yes' in 2, are you an in-house interpreter (working in a law office, police office, prosecutor office, court)? Or do you work in an agent?	
4.	If 'no' in 2, are you a freelancer? Then, what are you and where do you work?	-Freelancer -Work as tour guides -Teacher, lecturer -Work in hospitality -Work in Travel agent -Work in Law Office
5.	As a legal interpreter, where have you been working?	-Police Office
	How many times have you been in charge in the following Offices:	
	Police Office?	1-5
	Prosecutor Office?	1-2
	Court?	-
	Lawyer's office? (Assisting lawyer for meeting with foreign client?)	1-3
6.	Who did you serve in those offices? (Reported person, witness, suspect, alleged, accused, experts witness, etc.)	-Witness -client -reported/alleged person
7.	Who called you to be an interpreter in those offices?	-Friend asks for help -Friend gave my number to police, then police call -Lawyer -Suspect
8.	Who hired you as an interpreter?	-Lawyer -Police -Foreigner
Based on the results of research entitled "Legal Interpreters' Performance from Users' View" conducted in Police Offices in Badung and Denpasar Region, Prosecutor Office of Badung and Denpasar, and Kerobokan Prison (interviewing inmates), the following feedbacks were provided. What are your responses to the feedbacks?		
1. Did you agree to the feedbacks?		
2. Please give your comments, idea, reasons to the feedbacks.		
9.	Feedback from police officers: Communicative language competent of some interpreters is less of the four ratings: (1) poor, (2) less, (3) good, (4) excellent	(1) agree (no background of English) English spoken (2) is only for tour guiding (3) Acting as an interpreter because police officer asked, (4) Acting as ad hoc interpreter or preliminary only not for further process
10.	Feedback from police officers and lawyers: Some interpreters are lack of legal terms, they police officers need to speak repeatedly	(1) Never been an interpreter in the police office (2) Never learnt legal English (3) Only learnt general English in an English Course (4) Learnt English by speaking directly with foreigner (5) Difficulty in understanding English in Ner formal/legal situation ous due to unfamiliar with v the circumstances
11.	Feedback from police officers and lawyers: Some interpreters did not know the procedures of interrogation or investigation, as the result, the interrogation takes longer time.	(1) Never been an interpreter in the police office (2) Never read procedures of interrogation (3) Hard to translate Indonesian into English in formal situation vice versa
12.	Feedback from police officers: Some interpreters tend to interpret word per word.	(1) No English background, hard to translate longer utterance (2) Hard to understand native speaker particularly British English-speaking foreigner

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13.	Feedback from police officers: Some interpreters tend to help or stand on interrogatee's side.	(1) We are hired by the interrogatee or his/her lawyer (2) We have to help our client (3) We are afraid our client is not happy as the result we are not paid (4) Lawyer or family of the interrogatee requested us to do
14.	Feedback from police officers and lawyers: Some interpreters did not interpret part of question, even the key point (linguistic absence).	(1) Did not know the words (2) Did not know the legal term (3) Translate only what we knew (4) Did not know if we have to translate completely and accurately
15.	Feedback from police officers and lawyers: Some interpreters are less accurate in conveying messages from Police Officer vice versa.	Because of limited language competence (1) Lack of knowledge on legal language in Indonesian as well as English (3) No knowledge and experience of effective communication
16.	Feedback from Inmates: Some interpreters are lack of language competent (poor grammar, inaccurate pronunciation, even confusing)	No English background (1) English learnt from short course for working in hospitality (2) Never learnt pronunciation (4) Learnt English through listening music, or youtube
17.	Feedback from Inmates: Interpreter judged the inmates guilty.	(1) Got info from police or lawyer (2) Advised to inform it to the client.
18.	Feedback from Inmates: Interpreter advised the inmates to admit criminal action.	Advised to inform that by officer or Lawyer
19.	Feedback from Inmates: Interpreters advised the inmates to follow the direction of police or lawyers	Advised to say so by police or lawyer
20.	Feedback from Inmates: Interpreters gave suggestion to inmates to choose a lawyer	Interpreter is advised to suggest the client to choose certain lawyer
21.	Feedback from prosecutor: Some Interpreters acted partially for the benefit of the suspect/accused?	(1) Because we were paid by him/her (2) We were advised to do so by lawyer or family of the accused who paid us
22.	Feedback from prosecutor: Some interpreters did not know method of interpreting in court	(1) Never learnt about method of interpreting (2) Never took any course about method of interpreting (3) Never observed other interpreters in translating
23.	Feedback from prosecutor: Interpreter directed the accused in the examination.	(1) We want to help our client (the accused) (2) We were advised to do so by the lawyer (3) We were paid by our client

Table 1 above shows that the legal interpreters of this category engaged in interpretation tasks only occasionally, typically ranging from 1 to 4 time over a span of 1 to 2 years. A majority of them are employed in the area within the hospitality sector, junior or senior high school teaching, tour guiding, and paralegal positions in law firms. None of them has any plan to be a full-time interpreter. Their engagement in the interpreting work was due to their capability of speaking English. Their friends working at the police office asked them to help the police officer to take report or first interrogation. In some occasions, they were also requested by the lawyers or foreigners directly. Their role involves interpreting during initial interrogations of claimants, witnesses, individuals who have been alleged or reported, and occasionally suspects. Surely, they have no formal training or interpreting expertise. Consequently, they received various unfavorable evaluations from users such as law enforcement officers, attorneys, and assisted foreign individuals. Primarily, they acknowledged their limited language proficiency, both in terms of grammar and pronunciation, as they were not from English School. They learnt English through short courses, even learning by doing in the field.

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Their services as interpreters at the police office just to help the police in taking report and preliminary interrogation. But, then after the first occasion, they were requested again by the same police office.

Furthermore, they acknowledged their lack of acquaintance with legal English, intricate vocabulary, and appropriate interpreting techniques. Their absence of prior interpreting practice, absence of training or formal education in interpreting methods, and lack of exposure to structured and demanding scenarios left them feeling apprehensive. Consequently, they often relied on literal, verbatim translations, a result of their limited command of both the English language and legal jargon. This situation was exacerbated by their absence of an English language foundation, making the interpretation of lengthy statements challenging and comprehending conversations with English native speakers a significant hurdle for them.

Moreover, their limited exposure resulted in them disregarding ethical considerations for interpreters. Consequently, they frequently consented to aid foreign individuals, assuming they were being remunerated, and even extended their involvement to offering guidance. On multiple occasions, they opted not to translate specific terms or expressions that were unfamiliar to them in both English and Indonesian. An additional repercussion of their insufficient grasp of interpreter ethics was their inclination to directly steer and counsel the individual being interpreted, particularly when they perceived their compensation hinged on such actions.

B. Professional Interpreters

Table. 2 Professional Legal Interpreters' Responses to Users' Feedback

No.	Questions	Response
1.	<i>How long have you been practicing as legal interpreter?</i>	<i>More than two years</i>
2.	<i>Are you a full-time interpreter?</i>	<i>-3 years -Others no</i>
3.	<i>If 'yes' in 2, are you an in-house interpreter (working in a law office, police office, prosecutor office, court)? Or do you work in an agent?</i>	<i>-1 – in-house in a law firm -2 Freelance</i>
4.	<i>If 'no' in 2, are you a freelancer? Then, what are you and where do you work?</i>	<i>-1 – in-house interpreter in a law firm -Other - Freelancers -Work as tour guides -Teacher, lecturer -Work in hospitality -Work in Travel agent -Work in Law Office</i>
5.	<i>As a legal interpreter, where have you been working?</i>	<i>-Police Office -Prosecutor Office -Court -Custom -Immigration -Notary -Manpower Office -Lawyer's Office</i>
	<i>How many times have you been in charge in the following Offices:</i>	
	<i>a. Police Office?</i>	<i>More than 5 times</i>
	<i>b. Prosecutor Office?</i>	<i>More than 3 times</i>
	<i>c. Court?</i>	<i>More than 10 times</i>
	<i>d. Lawyer's office? (Assisting lawyer for meeting with foreign client?)</i>	<i>More than 3</i>
6.	<i>Who did you serve in those offices? (Reported person, witness, suspect, alleged, accused, experts witness, etc.)</i>	<i>-Claimants -Respondents -Witness -client -reported/alleged person -Parties to Agreements -Passengers carrying illegal goods -Workers' dispute -Clients</i>
7.	<i>Who called you to be an interpreter in those offices?</i>	<i>-Lawyers -Police -Prosecutors -Alternates clerk -Notary -Foreigners after obtaining contact number from police, lawyers, prosecutors, Notary -Others</i>
8.	<i>Who hired you as an interpreter?</i>	<i>-Lawyer</i>

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Notary -Police -Foreigner -Prosecutor
<p>Based on the results of research entitled "Legal Interpreters' Performance from Users'ed in Police Offices in Badung and Denpasar Region, Prosecutor Office of Badung and Denpasar, and Kerobokan Prison (interviewinggg feedbacks were provided. inmates), the followin What are your responses to the feedbacks?</p>		
3.	Did you agree to the feedbacks?	
4.	Please give your comments, idea, reasons to the feedbacks.	
9.	<p>Feedback from police officers: Communicative language competent of some interpreters is less of the four ratings: (1) poor, (2) less, (3) good, (4) excellent</p>	<p>(1) Not for professional or interpreter's members of HPI (2) Yes, perhaps for pop-up (ad hoc) or beginner interpreter</p>
10.	<p>Feedback from police officers and lawyers: Some interpreters are lack of legal terms, they police officers need to speak repeatedly</p>	<p>(1) True, various cases are encountered at the police (2) Never been an interpreter in the police office (3) Never learnt legal English (4) Only learnt general English (5) Difficulty in understanding English in formal/legal situation (6) Nervous due to unfamiliar with the circumstances</p>
11.	<p>Feedback from police officers and lawyers: Some interpreters did not know the procedures of interrogation or investigation, as the result, the interrogation takes longer time.</p>	<p>(1) Some interpreters perhaps, mostly know (2) Never been an interpreter in the police office (3) Never read procedures of interrogation (4) Hard to translate Indonesian into English in formal situation vice versa</p>
12.	<p>Feedback from police officers: Some interpreters tend to interpret word per word.</p>	<p>(1) It never happens to Professional Interpreters, the newer ones, it will not happen, (2) They got training provided by the association, etc.</p>
13.	<p>Feedback from police officers: Some interpreters tend to help or stand on interrogatee's side.</p>	<p>Yes, perhaps, particularly in-house (1) interpreters (2) Or interpreters more concerned to maintaining relationship (reputation). (3) We are hired by the interrogatee or his/her lawyer (4) We have to help our client (5) We are afraid our client is not happy as the result we are not paid (6) Lawyer or family of the interrogatee requested us to do</p>
14.	<p>Feedback from police officers and lawyers: Some interpreters did not interpret part of question, even the key point (linguistic absence).</p>	<p>(1) Not true, linguistic absence, perhaps occurs for conversation beyond interrogation, exchanges between police-police or other parties unrelated to the interrogation</p>
15.	<p>Feedback from police officers and lawyers: Some interpreters are less accurate in conveying messages from Police Officer vice versa.</p>	<p>(1) Some may [yes], due to lack of knowledge on legal language in Indonesian as well as English. (2) Cases changes, or new cases</p>

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16.	<i>Feedback from Inmates: Some interpreters are lack of language competent (poor grammar, inaccurate pronunciation, even confusing)</i>	<i>Not for professional interpreters. (1) Perhaps, the interpreters were lawyer's staff (2) (in-house interpreter and beginner)</i>
17.	<i>Feedback from Inmates: Interpreter judged the inmates guilty.</i>	<i>(1) True, particularly for in-house interpreter (2) Brief prior working by the lawyers, or the paying party (3) Directed by the police or lawyer (4) Advised to inform it to the client.</i>
18.	<i>Feedback from Inmates: Interpreter advised the inmates to admit criminal action.</i>	<i>(1) True, particularly for in-house interpreter (2) Brief prior working by the lawyers (3) Directed by the police or lawyer (4) Advised to inform it to the client.</i>
19.	<i>Feedback from Inmates: Interpreters advised the inmates to follow the direction of police or lawyers</i>	<i>(1) True, in-house interpreter or interpreter hired by the lawyer (2) Advised to say so by police or lawyer</i>
20.	<i>Feedback from Inmates: Interpreters gave suggestion to inmates to choose a lawyer</i>	<i>(1) Most prof. interpreter no. (2) True, for a few interpreters got advice and agree to do so (3) Interpreter is advised to suggest the client to choose certain lawyer</i>
21.	<i>Feedback from prosecutor: Some Interpreters acted partially for the benefit of the suspect/accused?</i>	<i>(1) Most interpreters no (2) A few yes, as they assumed that they were paid by him/her They were advised to do so by lawyer or family of the accused who paid us</i>
22.	<i>Feedback from prosecutor: Some interpreters did not know method of interpreting in court</i>	<i>True, not all legal interpreters have experiences working in court. (1) experiences working in court. (2) Never observed other interpreters in working in court</i>
23.	<i>Feedback from prosecutor: Interpreter directed the accused in the examination.</i>	<i>(4) Most interpreters no (5) A few yes, as they assumed that they were paid by him/her (6) They were advised to do so by lawyer or family of the accused who paid us (7) They want to help their client (the accused) (8) They were advised to do so by the lawyer (9) They were paid by their client</i>

Table 2 illustrates the responses of professional legal interpreters in relation to the feedback given by users. These skilled interpreters possess a high level of competence in English and are proficient in various interpreting methods, particularly within legal contexts. They maintain affiliations with professional associations and carry more than three years of practical experience. Among the ten adept interpreters who participated in the survey, three hold full-time positions, while the remaining seven operate as independent freelancers. Within the trio of full-time interpreters, one works as an in-house interpreter. Nevertheless, these interpreters did not fully align with the feedback provided by users. Among the fifteen feedback points submitted, a majority perceived the feedback as somewhat inaccurate. Nevertheless, some points were acknowledged for valid reasons: Firstly, due to the substantial caseload at police offices, interpreters might not possess comprehensive familiarity with all essential legal terminology. Furthermore, not all legal interpreters have been involved in police office proceedings, leading to an unfamiliarity with interrogation methods and procedures. Secondly, instances of interpreters demonstrating partiality and aiding foreign clients could be attributed to a lack of

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understanding of the ethical standards governing legal interpreters. Potential misunderstandings could arise from payment arrangements, briefings, and instructions received from supervisors (in the case of in-house interpreters) or from the police (for freelancers). The financial involvement of lawyers, foreigners, or the police could result in interpreters offering guidance, suggestions, and direction for foreigners to admit specific actions. However, only a minority of interpreters are inclined to engage in such behavior, with the majority refraining from such practices.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the result and discussion above, it can be concluded non-professional interpreters correspond to the ad hoc interpreters as described in the initial year of research. These interpreters of this category engage in interpretation tasks only occasionally, typically ranging from 1 to 4 instances over a span of 1 to 2 years. A majority of them are employed in roles within the hospitality sector, junior or senior high school teaching, tour guiding, and paralegal positions in law firms. Their role involves interpreting during initial interrogations of claimants, witnesses, individuals who have been alleged or reported, and occasionally suspects. These interpreters, lacking formal training or interpreting expertise, assumed their responsibilities due to their ability to communicate in general English. Consequently, they received various unfavorable evaluations from users such as law enforcement officers, attorneys, and assisted foreign individuals. Primarily, they acknowledged their limited language proficiency, both in terms of grammar and pronunciation. Additionally, they admitted unfamiliarity with legal English, specialized terminology, and proper interpreting methodologies. Consequently, they frequently resorted to literal word-by-word translations due to their deficient grasp of English and legal terminology. Furthermore, their lack of experience led them to overlook interpreter ethics. As a result, they often agreed to offer assistance to foreign individuals, believing they were being compensated, and even provided advice. On numerous occasions, they chose not to translate certain words or phrases if they were unfamiliar with them in either English or Indonesian. Another consequence of their inadequate understanding of interpreter ethics was their tendency to directly guide and advise the individual being interpreted, especially if they believed payment was contingent on doing so.

Professional interpreters, on the contrary, are skilled language mediators proficient in English, possessing expertise in various interpreting methods, especially in legal contexts. They are affiliated with professional associations and boast over three years of practical experience. Out of a group of 10 proficient interpreters who responded to the questionnaires, three are employed full-time, while the remaining seven operate as independent freelancers. Among the trio of full-time interpreters, one is stationed in-house. However, these interpreters did not completely concur with the feedback provided by users. Out of the fifteen feedback points submitted by users, a majority believed that the feedback was somewhat inaccurate. Nonetheless, some points were acknowledged for valid reasons: Firstly, considering the high volume of cases presented at the police office, the interpreters might not be wellversed in all the requisite legal terminology. Additionally, not all legal interpreters have been involved in police office proceedings, which results in an unfamiliarity with interrogation methods and procedures. Secondly, instances of interpreters displaying partiality and assisting foreign clients could stem from a lack of comprehension regarding the ethical guidelines governing legal interpreters. Misunderstandings might arise from payment arrangements, briefings, and directives received from supervisors (in the case of inhouse interpreters) or from the police (for freelancers). The involvement of lawyers, foreigners, or the police in their compensation might lead to interpreters providing advice, suggestions, and direction for foreigners to admit certain actions. However, only a small subset of interpreters is inclined to do so, while the majority refrains from such actions.

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